

Stability Constants and Related Thermodynamic Functions of Some Rare-Earth Metal Complexes of Sodium 2-[4-Amino-3-(1,2,4-Triazolylazo)]Naphthol-4-Sulphonate

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Manuscript received 23 July 1981, revised 17 December 1981, accepted 23 May 1982

The stability constants of La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Yb^{3+} and Y^{3+} complexes of sodium 2-[4-amino-3-(1,2,4-triazolylazo)]naphthol-4-sulphonate have been determined in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths and temperatures employing the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes involved in complexation have been determined.

THE stability constants of the complexes of sodium 2-[4-amino-3-(1,2,4-triazolylazo)]naphthol-4-sulphonate (ATN-4S) with some rare-earth metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹ and the results are reported in the present communication.

A Beckman Expandomatic SS-2 pH meter in conjunction with glass and calomel electrode assembly (0-14 pH range) was used for pH measurements. Constant temperature was maintained by using a thermostat fitted with a contact thermometer.

Experimental

The synthesis and characterisation of ATN-4S were reported earlier². Its solution was prepared in double distilled water. The nitrates of the rare-earths (99.99% pure) were procured from Indian Rare Earths Ltd., Bombay and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. In cases where nitrates were not available, the oxides were dissolved in nitric acid, the solutions were heated to dryness and the residues dissolved in double distilled water. All the solutions were standardised complexometrically using EDTA as the titrant. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain constant ionic strength. A 0.05 M standardised solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) was used as the titrant for potentiometric titrations.

The following solutions (total volume 25.0 ml) were titrated against standard TMAH solution: (i) 1.0 ml HClO_4 (0.05 M) + 1.5 ml NaNO_3 (0.02 M) + water, (ii) 1.0 ml HClO_4 (0.05 M) + 1.5 ml NaNO_3 (0.02 M) + 10.0 ml ATN-4S (0.05 M) + water, (iii) 1.0 ml HClO_4 (0.05 M) + 0.5 ml $\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (0.02 M) + 10.0 ml ATN-4S (0.05 M) + water.

All titrations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at the desired temperature, maintained

with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and with appropriate amounts of NaClO_4 to maintain the desired ionic strengths.

Results and Discussion

The pK_a value of the ligand has been obtained from a plot of $\log [\bar{n}_H/(1-\bar{n}_H)]$ vs pH and the values obtained at 30° and different ionic strengths, viz., 0.01 M, 0.05 M, 0.10 M and 0.20 M are 5.92, 5.85, 5.81 and 5.78, respectively. The pK_a values at 40° and 50° and $I=0.10$ M are 5.71 and 5.61, respectively. The pK_a value at zero ionic strength and 30° , obtained by extrapolation, is 5.96.

The $\bar{n}$ and pL data were subjected to the least squares treatment of Sullivan *et al.*³ to give β_n values. The stability constants thus calculated at three different temperatures and $I=0.10$ M are given in Table 1. In cases of ATN-4S complexes, the first two steps involved in complexation proceed almost simultaneously and hence in the case of most metals the step-wise stability constant values for the first two steps cannot be evaluated. Moreover, the lighter elements form only 1:2 complexes, while the heavier ones form 1:3 complexes also. Hence, $\log \beta_n$ values are most convenient for comparison as they are available for all the metals used.

A plot of $\log \beta_n$ vs $1/r$ (r =ionic radius) shows a regular increase from lanthanum to ytterbium with a break at gadolinium. The position of yttrium lies between gadolinium and terbium. In terms of electrostatic considerations, the gadolinium break may be attributed to the discontinuity of the crystal radius at gadolinium. However, this approach is based on the assumption that the trends in the crystal radii are reflected in the solvated as well as in the coordinated ions, which may not be entirely true⁴.

The gadolinium break may be explained in terms of the ligand field theory⁵. Crystal field

Effects due to presence of ligand may be operative^{5,6}, and there may be varying degree of interaction of the 4f orbital with the ligand field. No such stabilisation is expected for the Gd³⁺ ion. Rossotti⁷ questioned the validity of this suggestion, since on this basis the stability constants for Y³⁺ and Gd³⁺ complexes should be equal (both ions have no field stabilisations), but due to the smaller size of Y³⁺ ion, Y³⁺ complexes are expected to have higher stability than Gd³⁺ complexes. This has been observed in the present case.

The stability constants of the complexes have been found to decrease with increasing ionic strength of the medium, which is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel equation⁸.

The values of stability constants in Table 1 reveals that the stability constant value decreases

with increase in temperature. The ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values have been calculated⁹ and the results are shown in Table 2. ΔG values have

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE RARE-EARTH METAL COMPLEXES OF ATN-4S AT I=0.10 M NaClO₄

Cations	- $\Delta G(\beta_n)$ (KJ/mole)			- $\Delta H(\beta_n)$ KJ/mole	$\Delta S(\beta_n)$ (J/deg/mole)
	30°	40°	50°		
La ³⁺	65.27	64.00	61.88	57.90	24.32
Pr ³⁺	69.61	68.32	66.46	57.78	58.86
Nd ³⁺	72.46	70.90	69.00	56.35	53.30
Sm ³⁺	72.91	70.96	68.88	65.48	24.52
Gd ³⁺	74.59	73.00	70.85	66.84	25.58
Tb ³⁺	76.27	74.06	72.22	65.48	35.61
Dy ³⁺	79.70	77.90	76.32	54.84	82.08
Yb ³⁺	81.84	80.23	78.09	59.40	74.09
Y ³⁺	76.17	74.66	72.84	53.33	75.39

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (I=0.10 M NaClO₄)

Constant	Temp., °C		
	30	40	50
		La ³⁺	
log β_1	6.15	5.73	5.34
log β_2	11.25	10.68	10.00
		Pr ³⁺	
log β_1	6.71	6.30	5.73
log β_2	12.00	11.99	10.68
		Nd ³⁺	
log β_1	—	6.67	5.84
log β_2	12.49	11.83	11.16
log β_3	15.27	—	—
		Sm ³⁺	
log β_1	—	6.22	4.93
log β_2	12.57	11.80	11.24
log β_3	17.89	14.92	—
		Gd ³⁺	
log β_1	—	—	—
log β_2	12.60	12.04	11.35
log β_3	18.10	15.00	14.42
		Tb ³⁺	
log β_1	—	—	—
log β_2	13.15	12.85	11.68
log β_3	18.96	17.83	15.91
		Dy ³⁺	
log β_1	—	—	—
log β_2	13.74	13.00	12.32
log β_3	19.11	17.85	16.66
		Yb ³⁺	
log β_1	—	—	—
log β_2	14.11	13.39	12.63
log β_3	19.29	17.98	16.70
		Y ³⁺	
log β_1	—	—	—
log β_2	13.13	12.46	11.78
log β_3	18.66	17.23	15.83

been found to be negative in all cases, showing complex formation to be a spontaneous process. ΔG values have been found to increase with increase in temperature indicating that low temperature favours complexation. This is also confirmed by negative enthalpy values. The positive entropy values show increase in randomness in the systems indicating the presence of a larger number of species. However, the change in entropy for β_3 is negative, which indicates that randomness decreases in going from species ML₃ to ML₂. This might be due to the change in dentate character of the ligand or as a result of the increase in coordination number of the metal ion.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Centre of Advanced Studies in Chemistry, University of Delhi, for financial assistance to one of them (S. M.).

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